

Critical Analysis Of Integrating Technology As Pedagogy In South African Higher Education: A Literature Review

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: June 13, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: September 14, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Pedagogy, South Africa, Technological Devices, Traditional Teaching</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8345592</p>	<p><i>Pedagogy in the 21st century and beyond can never remain the same again following the advent and the continuous quest for the adoption of technology in its approaches. However, in underdeveloped and developing nations such as South Africa the rate of adoption is slow following different besetting factors. For instance, the pedagogic value of e-learning has been alluded as one of the most challenging for institutions of higher learning. Therefore, using the document analysis methodology, this study presents both benefits and challenges of integrating technology as pedagogy in the context of South African institutions of higher learning, and by extension underdeveloped and developing nations alike. The finding of the study shows that among others that though technology in pedagogical practices is paramount, it cannot replace traditional methods of teaching. However, the use of technology in teaching and learning aids traditional forms of pedagogy. The study therefore recommends among others that there is need for the provision of technological devices and sensitization of teachers and learners in the adjustment of pedagogy due to the inclusion of technology.</i></p>

Introduction

Technology is rapidly changing the world in all spheres of life (Cascio &Montealegre, 2016; United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, n.d)), education inclusive (Zhang, 2022; Altun, Khurshid Ahmad, 2021). Other sectors such as economic (Solomon & van Klyton, 2020; Qureshi, 2020), health (Humanitas University, 2021; Rauv, 2021), information and business communication (Dawairi, 2022; Anand, 2021; Natter, 2019), among others are all affected. This is confirmed by Ngoc Hoang and Hung (2020, p. 1) indicating that technology ‘becomes the main vehicle of a new society’. Furthermore, these scholars allude that technology has become an integral part of the knowledge society and influences people's behaviour. This implies that the education system has a huge role to play in promoting the use of technology in the transfer of knowledge as supported by Ngoc Hoang and Hung (2020). This is contrary to the reverse which is a common notion and major submission by different scholars as well as institutions that technology enhances education (Agrawal, 2022; Ganimian, Vegas & Hess, 2022; TrustRadius, 2022; American University, 2020). In most instances, this submission is upheld without taking cognizance of education promoting the use of technology. This suggests that while technology enhances teaching and learning, it is also aided and promoted by the education system. Meanwhile, it is worthy of note that technology is a relevant tool that can be utilized to improve the education system. To be more specific, teaching methods must be used to develop and transfer specific skills that serve both the purposes of knowledge development and dissemination, while also preparing graduates for work in a knowledge-based society. Therefore, integrating technology as pedagogy is relevant for students to keep abreast until they graduate. It enables closing the gap between the employer, the institution, and the graduates. Meanwhile, implementing technology in teaching and learning, involves different categories or groups of persons such as students, teachers or instructors, administrators, and technical and other support staff (Zhang, 2022; Aghaei, Rajabi, Lie, Ajam, 2020; Khan, 2010). Furthermore, the incorporation of technology as a pedagogy may have both positive and negative consequences. Against this backdrop, this study aims to analyse the benefits and challenges of integrating technology as a pedagogy within the context of South African higher education institutions. This paper uses desktop research by analysis secondary sources, a method of gathering data from existing literature (Juneja, 2015). Aside from the introduction, the paper is divided into three sections. First, it discusses the conceptual and theoretical framework that underpins this study; second, it discusses the integration of technology as a pedagogy, its promises, and limitations; and finally, it focuses on the conclusion.

Conceptual and Theoretical Framework

This section includes a discussion of the concepts, such as technology and pedagogy, as well as the framework therein. In addition, theories developed in the integration of technology as pedagogy is presented and duly discussed. As a result, this section is divided into two subsections: Conceptual framework (1) and theoretical framework (2).

Conceptual framework

The concept 'technology' originates from the Greek word '*tekne*' which relates to art and craft and 'logia' which means study (Kumar, 2022). The combination of both words, *teknologia*, means systematic treatment. (Kumar, 2022). Moreover, Ford & Cena (2021, p. 14) define technology as

the application of scientific knowledge for practical purposes or applications. [The] technology uses scientific principles and applies them to change the environment in which humans live. Technology can also use scientific principles to advance industry or other human constructions. Problems exist in the human environment and have for all of history. The existence of problems is what creates technological advancement; where there is struggle and tension, there is ingenuity and creativity. From this environment comes technology: ways in which the human experience is improved by the invention of objects that solve a problem.

The identified definition above, indicates that technology can be used to solve human problems. Likewise, technology is used in and for education (Mnisi, 2022). There is a difference between the two concepts. On the other hand, where relevant tools such as the internet, computers, software, audio and visual, and projectors are available. One can speak of 'technology in education (Mnisi, 2022), whereas 'technology for higher education refers to the incorporation of technological theories into teaching and learning (Mnisi,2022). This paper focuses on the latter concept. Technology for learning is also referred to as educational technology, which is defined as the process of analysing, designing, developing, implementing, and evaluating the online environment, learning materials, learners, and learning processes to improve teaching and learning. (Loyola, 2021). Moreover, Khan (2010, p1) considers educational technology as 'E-learning, He describes this process as

Innovative approach for delivering a well-designed, learner-centered, interactive, and facilitated learning environment to anyone, anyplace, anytime, by utilizing the attributes and resources of various digital technologies along with other forms of learning materials suited for an open and distributed learning environment.

According to the above definition, e-learning should be accessible, interactive, and flexible. This accounts for one of the reasons for the development of an e-learning framework by Khan (2010). The e-learning framework includes eight dimensions: institutional, management, technological, pedagogical, ethical, interface design, resource support, and evaluation. Sequel to the e-learning framework by Khan (2010), the authors adopted a table to outline various identified issues that are associated with the dimensions. This is because the same framework is used to underpin the e-learning concepts discussed in this paper. Following submissions from reviewed literature, the authors saw the need to include an additional dimension known as 'national (government)' to the table below. Thus, the table 1 below contains nine dimensions of e-learning following reviewed literature and adaptation from Khan (2010) e-learning framework.

Table 1: The E-learning Framework adapted from Badrul Khan.

Dimensions of e-learning	Summary of issues related to dimension
National (government)	❖ Socio-economic benefits
Institutional	❖ Administrative affairs ❖ Academic Affairs ❖ Students' services
Management	❖ People, process, and product ❖ Team ❖ e-learning content development ❖ e-learning environment
Technological	❖ Infrastructure planning ❖ Hardware ❖ software
Pedagogical	❖ Content analysis ❖ Audience analysis

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Goal analysis ❖ Design Approach ❖ Instructional strategies
Ethical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Bias and Political ❖ Issues Geographical ❖ Diversity Learner ❖ Diversity Digital ❖ Divide ❖ Etiquette ❖ Legal Issues
Interface design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Page and Site Design Content ❖ Design Navigation ❖ Accessibility ❖ Usability ❖ Testing
Resource support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Online Support ❖ Resources
Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Evaluation of Content Development Process ❖ Evaluation of E-Learning Environment Evaluation of E-Learning at the Program and Institutional Levels ❖ Assessment of Learner

Sequel to table 1, it is worth noting that these factors are inextricably linked and interdependent, and they all contribute to the creation of a meaningful learning environment. (Khan, 2010). Furthermore, Khan (2010), while discussing the eight dimensions of e-learning, allows other researchers to think critically and expand the e-learning dimension. This paper agrees with Khan and adds a national dimension to the table above. The addition of a national dimension stems from the submission of different scholars such as Makgahlela, Mothiba, Mokwena and Mphekgwana, (2021), Aedo, Nahata and Sabarwal (2020), Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) (2020) and Jung (2011), that there is need for government to support high-quality e-learning. This is in a bid to maximize socioeconomic benefits (Bubou& Job, 2021; Eze, Chinedu-Eze, Okike& Bello, 2020). Suffice to state that government support of e-learning benefits the citizenry in various ways such as access (Innocent &Masue, 2020; Arkorful&Abaidoo, 2014; Ndoje, 2013), enhances changes and quality in education (Innocent &Masue, 2020; Lwoga&Komba, 2015), as well as tackles issues of socio-economic challenges. Review of the works of Arkorful and Abaidoo (2014) and Khan (2005) show that one of the major benefits to be enjoyed by South Africa as a nation with regards to integrating technology as pedagogy is the combat with inequality. South Africa has been recognised and described as the most unequal nation in the world (University of Cape Town News, 2021; Stats SA, 2020; Mlaba, 2020), while the works of Arkorful and Abaidoo (2014) and Khan (2005) explain that the integration of technology as pedagogy is envisaged to help in the provision of equal access to teaching and learning materials. Suffice to state that South Africa may be able to somewhat combat challenges surrounding unequal access to quality education should due diligence be given to the integration of technology as pedagogy. This is in congruence with the works of Walker, Pearce, Boe and Lawson (2019) who hold the view that integration of technology as pedagogy is capable of reducing inequalities in diverse forms and ways. However, this is in contrast with Ugalde, and González-CabreraCecilia (2016) which indicates that ICT in education is capable of increasing inequality. Thus, as much as the integration of technology as pedagogy may be able to help combat inequalities, it may be unable to eradicate it entirely. In some instances, it may increase the rate of inequality. Hence, caution is needed.

In addition to technology, there is a concept of pedagogy that is relevant to this discourse. Pedagogy is defined by Gudaji (2019, p. 315) as ‘the exercises of instructing or educating, the exercises that confer knowledge or aptitude.’ Pedagogy is also explained by Zogla (2018) to mean an “interdisciplinary, ... functions as the theory or science and teachers in professional philosophy, academic discipline and practice, meets the general requirements to achieve educational, developmental and educative goals in their integrated quality; and these are in compliance with the integrity of human is physical, mental and social nature” (p. 33). Gudaji (2019) identifies five pedagogical approaches: constructivism, collaborative, inquiry-based, integrative, and reflective. The constructive approach assumes that learning occurs when students actively participate in the process of meaning and knowledge construction rather than passively receiving information (Gudaji, 2019). Inquiry-based learning is a type of active learning that begins with the posing of questions, problems, or scenarios rather than simply

presenting facts or depicting a straightforward path to knowledge (Gudaji, 2019). A facilitator is usually present to help with the process. Inquirers will identify and investigate issues and questions to broaden their knowledge or develop solutions (Gudaji, 2019). Integrative learning is a learning theory that describes a trend toward more integrated lessons that help students make cross-curricular connections (Gudaji, 2019). The process by which teachers examine their teaching practices, analyse how something was taught, and consider how the practice could be improved or changed to improve learning outcomes, is known as reflective teaching (Gudaji, 2019).

From the foregoing, it can be deduced that while integrating technology as pedagogy, as an e-learning framework, teachers should bear in mind the nine dimensions as displayed in the above table. In addition, the teacher needs to select a pedagogical approach linking to the choice of technology, that pedagogical approach depends on the module that will be delivered. Moreover, instructional models such as ASSURE, ADDIE, KEMP, and blended learning are available to help teachers design and implement course content (Mnisi, 2022). Although a detailed discussion of these models is not part of the discussion, let us explain their meaning briefly. ASSURE: the acronym stands for Analyze Learners, State Objectives, Select Instructional Methods, Media, and Materials, Utilize Media and Materials Require Learner Participation, Evaluate and Revise (Mnisi, 2022). ADDIE: Analysis, Design, Develop, Implement, Evaluate. (Mnisi, 2022). KEMP: sometimes referred to as the Morrison, Ross, and Kemp Model, has the four elements of design that are an integral part of course development: students, objectives, methods, and evaluation. (Instructional Designer handbook, n.d). Blended Learning is a collection of learning methods that combines online digital media with traditional classroom methods. (Acer for education, 2020). As previously stated, each teacher will employ a suitable model for his or her instruction. Unizulu is currently employing a hybrid approach. We combine online and traditional teaching methods here. The next section presents the theories adopted for this study.

Theoretical framework.

This paper investigates three relevant theories that underpin technology integration as pedagogy: E-learning theory, TPACK theory, and connectivism theory. In the context of this study, the network theory which may also be considered relevant is not taken into cognizance, rather e-learning, TPACK and Connectivism theories are preferred. Thus, the study focuses on the three theories which are as highlighted and explained below.

E-learning theory

According to Clark & Major (2016), E-learning theory is concerned with the use of educational technology to promote effective learning by reducing extraneous cognitive load and managing germane and intrinsic loads at appropriate levels for students. It can be difficult for teachers to design tasks at an appropriate level for their students; the e-learning theory model can assist teachers in understanding how cognitive load can be categorized and combined with design principles to facilitate effective learning with technology. (Clark & Major, 2016).

TPACK theory

Santos and Castro (2021) encapsulate the seven elements previously developed by Koehler and Misra to clearly explain the TPACK theory. These seven elements, according to Santos and Castro, are at the heart of good teaching:

1. ***Pedagogical knowledge (PK)***: Pedagogical knowledge refers to the methods and processes of teaching and includes knowledge in classroom management, assessment, lesson plan development, and student learning.
2. ***Technology knowledge (TK)***: Technology knowledge refers to the knowledge about various technologies, ranging from low-tech technologies such as pencil and paper to digital technologies such as desktop computers, internet connection, laptops, monitors for projection/television, printer, projector, scanner, speaker, tablet, etc.
3. ***Content Knowledge (CK)***: Content knowledge is the “knowledge about actual subject matter that is to be learned or taught”. Teachers must know about the content they are going to teach and how the nature of knowledge is different for various content areas.
4. ***Pedagogical content knowledge (PCK)***: Pedagogical content knowledge refers to the content knowledge that deals with the teaching process. Pedagogical content knowledge is different for various content areas, as it blends both content and pedagogy with the goal being to develop better teaching practices in the content areas.
5. ***Technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK)***: Technological pedagogical knowledge refers to the knowledge of how various technologies can be used in teaching, and to understand that using technology may change the way teachers teach.

- 6. Technological content knowledge (TCK):** Technological content knowledge refers to the knowledge of how technology can create new representations for specific content. It suggests that teachers understand that, by using a specific technology, they can change the way learners practice and understand concepts in a specific content area.
- 7. Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK):** Technological pedagogical content knowledge refers to the knowledge required by teachers for integrating technology into their teaching in any content area. Teachers have an intuitive understanding of the complex interplay between the three basic components of knowledge (CK, PK, TK) by teaching content using appropriate pedagogical methods and technologies.

Arguably, the above summary shows that a teacher's knowledge of a specific subject (content knowledge) and how they teach (pedagogical content) are not sufficient; technological knowledge is also required. The writer will apply the TPACK theory in her pedagogy.

Connectivism Theory

According to Siemens (2005), Connectivism is the integration of principles explored by chaos, network, and complexity theories, as well as self-organization theories. Learning is a process that takes place in hazy environments with shifting core elements that are not entirely under the individual's control. (Siemens, 2010). 'Learning (defined as actionable knowledge) can exist outside of ourselves (within an organization or a database), is focused on connecting specialized information sets, and the connections that allow us to learn more are more important than our current state of knowledge. (Siemens, 2005). What follows from Siemens' statement is the connection and flow of information, which results in knowledge existing beyond the individual.

Integrating technology as pedagogy Benefits and challenges

As alluded to above, society is rapidly transforming into a new form. Ngoc Hoang and Hung (2020) refer to that society as 'the information and knowledge society. This technological transformation is of utmost relevance as it bridges the gap between universities and society, by making institutions more flexible and accessible. (Guardia et al, 2021). However, it is noteworthy that technological integration as pedagogy is a complex phenomenon that involves a wide range of stakeholders, including teachers, students, higher education institutions, and managers, as well as the higher education department (Government). The motivations, perceptions, and beliefs of those stakeholders should be considered for the effective implementation of educational technology. As with any new technology, educational technology presents both opportunities and challenges.

One of the major issues is the socioeconomic disparity that affects students from low-income families. They are having difficulty accessing material online and have poor connectivity (Arubela & Jere, 2022). It is proposed by Cuisia-Villanova and Nufiez (2020) that socioeconomic status and accessibility are intertwined. For instance, in the South African context, the lower the social status of a household, the more likely its members are envisaged to experience difficulty in accessing education (Cuisia-Villanova & Nufiez, 2020; Andrew, et al 2020). This is described by Mpungose (2020) as an issue of social divide. This is considered to be a burden to institutions of higher learning who tend to struggle in providing modern physical resources to students for successful e-learning (Mpungose, 2020). Nonetheless, despite the challenges experienced, e-learning possesses potential benefits to different education stakeholders such as the government (Department of Higher education and Training) (Bagarukayo & Kalema, 2015), institutions of higher learning (Queiros & de Villiers, 2016), students (Al Rawashdeh, A. Z., et al 2021; Gupta, 2017; Queiros & de Villiers, 2016; Bagarukayo & Kalema, 2015), management and staff of institutions of higher learning (Mentis, 2021; Innocent & Masue, 2020), among others.

Furthermore, other research conducted by scholars such as Arubela and Jere (2022), Mnisi (2022), Guardia et al (2021), Cuisia-Villanova and Nufiez (2020), Keengee (2008), indicate some promises and challenges experienced by the different education stakeholders: government, institutions of higher learning, among others. This research summarises those promises and challenges in the table 2 below, thereafter, conclusion is drawn and recommendations made on how some challenges could be possibly addressed and promises duly enjoyed.

Table 2: Summary of benefits and challenges in educational technology.

Stakeholder	benefits	Challenges/limitations
Government/ Department of Higher education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Enhance teaching and learning ▪ Build a bridge between 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Digital disruption ▪ Unequal access ▪ Digital divide

	<p>universities and society.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ongoing support in digital teaching methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Democratise education
Institution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Promote pro-change attitude ▪ Funding ▪ Political support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Technological infrastructure, hardware, software ▪ Lack of digital and media competence ▪ Increase cost ▪ Maintenance of facilities ▪ Impact of academic policy on technological application ▪ Cyber security. ▪ Phishing emails.
Managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Funding ▪ Training of staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ongoing maintenance and regular updating of systems (computers, laptops, wifi networks, software, and databases)
Teachers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Increase access to the internet ▪ Fear of being replaced ▪ Issues of privacy ▪ Integrating digital learning with existing instructional content 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of equipment ▪ Resistance to change ▪ Diversity of students ▪ Lack of support ▪ Negative attitudes towards computer ▪ Lack of time ▪ Constraints on training and support ▪ Digital immigrants
Students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Digital natives ▪ Learn at your own pace ▪ Several learning opportunities ▪ Instant access to massive resources ▪ Collaborative learning ▪ Globalization ▪ Internationalization ▪ Data repository in one location ▪ Students are prepared for the future world. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Digital divide ▪ Increase cheating ▪ Poor students cannot access ▪ More distractions in the classroom ▪ Unreliable data and resources ▪ Unable to manage time ▪ Plagiarism ▪ Overreliance on info provider ▪ Computer Vision syndrome

Conclusion and recommendations

The purpose of this paper was to elaborate on the impact of integrating technology as a pedagogy. It was necessary to provide the study's background, conceptual and theoretical framework, and then elaborate on the impact of integrating technology as pedagogy. The study findings showed that although technology is commonly known to enhance education (teaching and learning process), it is however improved and promoted by the education system. Thus, both technology and education system can be considered as working *pari passu*. Also, whilst, technology cannot fully replace traditional teaching methods, in the context of South African institutions of higher learning, it helps to improve traditional forms of pedagogy. As a result, the following recommendations are made in the advent that effective educational technology are to be embraced for teaching and learning in order to enhance learning abilities of students in South African institutions of higher learning:

- The department responsible for higher education should provide more funds to assist students from low-income households in order to enhance their distance learning practices. This can be done in form of scholarship grants, call for supports from education stakeholders, Non-profit or non-governmental organizations (NPOs and NGOs), among others.
- Sensitization on the need for the inclusion of technology in teaching and learning would be needed for both teachers and students. Thus, periodic trainings, workshops, seminars, among others targeted at sensitizing both the students and their teachers can be organised by the Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET), as well as other responsible bodies. Schools can also engage parents in special sessions where they are sensitized on the need to support such venture by contributing their own quota, regardless of how little it may seem.
- Policies of institutions of higher learning should be student-centred rather than teacher-centred when it comes to active learning. This would help in ensuring that teachers adopt technology for teaching and learning exercises to the benefits of the students.
- There is a need for teacher collaboration or dialogue between institutions or at the institutional level where they can share ideas about how to integrate technology as pedagogy. It is a type of collaborative learning that can be accomplished through various platforms.

Limitation and suggestion for further study

This conceptual study is limited to reviews of literature which were considered relevant. Also, the study was limited to the context of South Africa. It is therefore suggested that similar study be replicated using quantitative and/or qualitative or mixed method approach using selected institutions of higher learning within and outside South Africa.

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